

COLOUR MEASUREMENTS OF THERMOCHROMIC INDICATORS WITH VARIOUS COLOURATION TEMPERATURES

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Abstract: *Defining dynamic colour change is one of the main tasks in the development of thermochromic indicators that can be applied to packaging. This study presents an approach to measure a dynamic colour change of six thermochromic samples that differ in colouration temperatures in the range of – 70 °C to 200 °C. A Fibre optic spectrometer connected to a custom-made measuring chamber together with a custom-made light source was applied to address several challenges that need to be considered in colour measurements of thermochromic indicators. Results show that the designed set-up is suitable for acquisition of colour coordinates of thermally treated samples in the studied temperature range.*

Keywords: thermochromism; colour measurements; dynamic colour change

1 INTRODUCTION

Packaging of goods mainly serves to protect, contain, promote, and inform about its content. In the case of sensitive goods, there are attempts to include speciality indicators in/on a packaging to communicate the current or previous conditions under which the good is or was transported (Fuertes *et al.*, 2016). Such an intelligent packaging can include a thermochromic indicator to provide information about temperature (Gunde *et al.*, 2011; Wang *et al.*, 2015). More sophisticated systems even contain simple electronic circuits for interaction with internal or/and external peripherals (Sima *et al.*, 2017). Nevertheless, the

simplest and most user-friendly identification is by a quick visual evaluation of the appearance of the indicator, which could also be included in automated video control. In this case, colour plays a crucial role.

There are many examples of reversible thermochromic materials that can estimate the actual temperature of the object (Kulčar *et al.*, 2010; Gunde *et al.*, 2011; Jakovljević *et al.*, 2016). To evaluate the dynamic colour change of thermochromic materials, it is necessary to perform colour measurements in dependence on the temperature.

The colour coordinates of the thermally treated thermochromic sample can be acquired by spectrometers or digital cameras. In the literature benchtop (Kulčar *et al.*, 2010), handheld (Panák *et al.*, 2012; Friškovec *et al.*, 2013), or fibre optic spectrometers (Rožić *et al.*, 2020; Stržić Jakovljević *et al.*, 2020) are reported. Other methods use digital cameras for non-contact measurements (Panák *et al.*, 2018; Booth *et al.*, 2021). Temperature control can be performed by water circulation connected to a regulated bath reservoir (Kulčar *et al.*, 2010; Panák *et al.*, 2012; Friškovec *et al.*, 2013; Panák *et al.* 2015; Rožić *et al.*, 2020; Stržić Jakovljević *et al.*, 2020), or by regulated units including Peltier elements (Panák *et al.*, 2018; Booth *et al.*, 2021).

MyCol d.o.o. is currently developing irreversible thermochromic indicators that can be produced by conventional printing techniques. These indicators can serve in a variety of applications and are aimed at identifying temperatures that exceed a certain value immediately or later. The range of temperatures varies from far as $-70\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ to that possibly exceeding $200\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. Since a colour change plays a crucial role in the indication of temperature, the assessment of a colour change is a key process in the development of such products. This contribution introduces a unique solution developed by MyCol, d.o.o. to obtain non-contact measurement in a wide range of temperatures in an isolated atmosphere.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Samples

Temperature indicators with various temperature regions of their activation have been prepared. The thermochromic inks developed and produced by MyCol d.o.o. were applied on the surface of the self-adhesive paper label MP CHROM 80 F KRSO (Mufлон, d.o.o). In this study, six indicators, I_{180} , I_{115} , I_{90} , I_{60} , R_{-20} , R_{-65} , were measured. The letters I and R denote a type of

indicator: irreversible and reversible, respectively. The number denotes the approximate activation temperature at which the colouration appears.

2. 2 Sample tempering

The tempering of the samples was carried out with the Temperature Controlled Plates HGP-01 and the Temperature Controlled Plate HGP-02 (Kambič d.o.o.) specially designed for the measurements of thermochromic labels. The HGP-01 device consists of two cooling/heating plates, Cold and Hot, and HGP-02 of one cooling/heating plate of 40 mm × 40 mm size. The temperature range for the Cold side of HGP-01 is from -7° to $+95^{\circ}$ °C, while the Hot side has a range from $+40$ to $+250^{\circ}$ °C. The temperature range of the HGP-02 device is from -100 to 10° °C. Each plate is regulated by its own microprocessor controller and can be connected to a computer with software supplied by the producer. This software allows for setting up the program of operation in the heating-cooling regime of the device and data recording (temperature and time).

2. 3 Colour measurements

There are several challenges that are addressed in the colour measurements of thermochromic samples. The applied measuring system should be able to withstand the temperature range of the heated/cooled sample. In our case, it is an interval from -100° °C to 250° °C that the HGP-01 and HGP-02 plates cover. The measuring system must be totally isolated from the sample, so that it cannot withdraw the heating/cooling energy from the heated/cooled sample. These two factors need non-contact measurements, where the probe is in a distance from the measured surface. Our setup utilises a fibre optic spectrometer HR4000 (Ocean Insight) connected to OceanView 2.0.8 application software through which the spectral and colorimetric data were recorded (reflectance, CIELAB coordinates, and time).

It must also be ensured that the outer environment (especially lighting) is not influencing the measurement. For this reason, the measuring system shall be a closed system. At freezing temperatures, it must be ensured that the measurement is not influenced by the fogging of the optical elements applied in the measuring system. To address these issues, we built a closed chamber with connectors through which nitrogen gas can be blown in and out. The chamber has a collimation lens, which is approximately 20 mm from the sample surface and collects reflected light at the sample normal. Light is collected from an area of about 3 mm in diameter and transmitted by optical fibre (600 μ m) to the spectrometer. The light from a light source is transmitted

along a bifurcated optical fibre ($2 \times 600 \mu\text{m}$) to the measuring chamber and illuminates the sample from 45° and -45° from the sample normal. The measuring chamber is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: The measuring chamber

Another challenging factor is a light source with sufficient intensity and a good spectral power distribution throughout the visible region. It should have limited emission in the NIR spectral region to protect the heating of the sample by the light source. To address these issues, we have built our own light source using full spectrum LED chip SKU YJ-VTC-135L-G01-56 (Beijing Yuji International Co., Ltd). This light source was aimed to replace the conventional halogen light source DH-2000 (Ocean Optics), which exhibited some limitations in intensity (long integration time) and lack of energy in the short wavelength region of visible spectrum.

2.4 Procedures

Comparison of light sources was done by measuring the reflectance of the white Spectralon (Labsphere) calibration standard. The integration time for each light source was set to have sufficient intensity of the signal, about 12 000 counts of maximum. The boxcar width was set to 5. The recorded range was 390–720 nm with a native reporting interval.

Thermochromic indicators were stuck on heating/cooling plate. The measurement setup was calibrated on the white Spectralon standard using a custom-built light source. The measuring chamber was attached to the heating/cooling plates GHP-01/GHP-02. When necessary (low temperature measurements), nitrogen was blown in the chamber at higher rate before measurement started to deplete moisture and avoid condensation on the sample surface. The rate of nitrogen flow was then reduced during the measurement. The recorded data on the time temperature of the heated /

cooled plate, together with the data on the time colorimetric coordinates, were evaluated and the dynamic colour change in terms of colour difference ΔE^*_{ab} in dependence on the temperature was visualised. The ΔE^*_{ab} was calculated with respect to the state with the lowest temperature.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Comparison of light sources

Figure 2 represents the spectral distribution in the relative counts reflected from the white Spectralon standard. Custom built LED light source gives more energy below 470 nm and lower energy above 630 nm. It does not emit in the near-IR region. The signal in the blue region reflected from the white standard seemed to be more stable over time in the case of the LED light source, which improved the calibration stability.

Figure 2: Spectra of LED (custom build) and DH-2000 halogen (Ocean Optics) light sources

3.2 Colour measurements of thermochromic indicators

The dynamic colour change of the thermochromic samples described in Chapter 2.1 measured with a custom-built chamber and a custom-built LED light source is shown in Figure 3. The colour measurement system presented in this study proves to be applicable in measurements of dynamic colour change of reversible and irreversible thermochromic indicators operating in a wide range of temperatures. It is possible to obtain colour coordinates at very low temperatures without unwanted humidity condensation. Reversible thermochromic indicators R_{-20} and R_{-65} exhibit typical hysteresis of similar type reversible thermochromic materials of. In the case of irreversible indicators, the colour changes only upon heating.

Figure 3: Dynamic colour change of thermochromic indicators with diverse colouration temperatures. Letters I and R denote irreversible and reversible indicators, respectively. The number denotes the approximate activation temperature. Letters C and H denote the cooling and heating direction, respectively.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Here we tested the custom-built measuring setup designed to evaluate the dynamic colour change of thermochromic indicators. The unique solution has proven its applicability in wide temperature range, from $-70\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ to $200\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, as shown in six reversible and irreversible thermochromic indicators with various activation temperatures. Humidity condensation was restricted by nitrogen flow in a closed measuring chamber. The good quality of a signal recorded by the fibre optic spectrometer was achieved by application of a custom-built LED light source.

These are the first measurements made with the custom-built system presented. They are the only colour measurements of thermochromic indicators reported over such a wide temperature region. The full range of temperatures ($-100\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ to $250\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$) will be possible to test after the preparation of the relevant thermochromic indicators.

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